

Impact of Dar es Salaam Port Expansion on Hinterland Road Network Traffic Performance

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Abstract:

Dar es Salaam Port is Tanzania's principal maritime gateway and a key regional hub serving several landlocked countries in East and Central Africa. Ongoing expansion under the Dar es Salaam Maritime Gateway Project is expected to increase cargo throughput and freight movement, placing additional pressure on the surrounding hinterland road network. This study evaluated the impact of port expansion on the performance of Kilwa Road (T007), Nyerere Road (T024), Mandela Road (T025), and Morogoro Road (T001). A macroscopic traffic model was developed in PTV Visum using traffic counts, road inventory data, cargo throughput statistics, and network information. Origin-Destination matrices were estimated using the Gravity Model and assigned through User Equilibrium traffic assignment. Model validation achieved a GEH value of 1.58 and an R² value of 0.99, indicating excellent agreement with observed traffic volumes. Four scenarios were analysed: existing conditions without port expansion, existing conditions with port expansion, a 20-year forecast with port expansion under a do-nothing approach, and a 20-year forecast incorporating infrastructure improvements. Results indicate that port expansion increases traffic volumes, Vehicle Hours Travelled (VHT), delays, and V/C ratios while reducing travel speeds and LOS. Under the future do-nothing scenario, all major corridors operated at LOS F with V/C ratios of 1.06-1.68. However, corridor widening and dedicated freight lanes reduced average VHT from 310 to 148.75 hours, increased average speed from 17.29 to 34.21 km/h, and improved LOS to A-D. The findings highlight the need to integrate port expansion with strategic transport infrastructure improvements.

Keywords: Dar es Salaam Port, Hinterland Road Network, Traffic Performance, Freight Transport, PTV Visum.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Dar es Salaam Port is the largest and busiest seaport in Tanzania and serves as the principal maritime gateway for both domestic and regional trade. The port handles approximately 95% of Tanzania’s maritime cargo and provides access to international markets for several landlocked countries in East and Central Africa, including Zambia, Rwanda, Burundi, Uganda, Malawi, and the Democratic Republic of Congo (World Bank, 2017);(TPA, 2022) Owing to increasing trade demand and cargo throughput, the Government of Tanzania has implemented the Dar es Salaam Maritime Gateway Project (DMGP), which includes berth rehabilitation, channel dredging, modernization of cargo handling facilities, and expansion of port infrastructure to improve operational efficiency and increase cargo handling capacity (TPA, 2022). Figure 1: illustrate the of Dar es salaam port and landlocked countries

Figure 1: Dar es Salaam port and landlocked countries

While these developments are expected to enhance trade competitiveness and logistics efficiency, they are also anticipated to generate substantial additional freight traffic on the surrounding hinterland road network. Major corridors serving the port, namely Kilwa Road (TO07), Nyerere Road (TO24), Mandela Road (TO25), and Morogoro Road (TO01), play a critical role in facilitating the movement of goods between the port, inland container depots, industrial areas, logistics centres, and regional trade corridors. As cargo throughput increases, these corridors are expected to experience higher traffic volumes, which may result in congestion, increased travel times, reduced travel speeds, higher vehicle operating costs, and deterioration of overall network performance(Rodrigue, 2020).

Previous studies have largely focused on port operations, logistics performance, and the economic benefits of port expansion, while limited attention has been given to

the impacts of port-induced traffic growth on the performance of hinterland road networks (Niu et al., 2024) and (Gan & Weng, 2024). Consequently, there remains a need to quantify the effects of port expansion on traffic conditions and evaluate infrastructure interventions capable of accommodating future demand. This study evaluates the impact of Dar es Salaam Port expansion on major hinterland road corridors using a macroscopic traffic modelling approach in PTV Visum and assesses the effectiveness of proposed improvement measures in mitigating congestion and enhancing network performance.

1.1 Problem statement

The expansion of Dar es Salaam Port is expected to increase cargo throughput and freight vehicle movements on major hinterland corridors, including Kilwa Road (T007), Nyerere Road (T024), Mandela Road (T025), and Morogoro Road (T001). Increased traffic demand may lead to congestion, longer travel times, reduced travel speeds, and deterioration in overall road network performance.

Despite the strategic importance of the port and its ongoing expansion, the impacts of port-induced traffic growth on the surrounding road network have not been comprehensively quantified. In particular, limited studies have applied transport modelling techniques to evaluate current and future traffic conditions under different port development scenarios. Therefore, there is a need for a systematic evaluating of the effects of Dar es Salaam Port expansion on hinterland road network performance and the effectiveness of potential infrastructure improvement measures.

1.2 Objectives

- a. To assess the current traffic performance of major hinterland corridors serving Dar es Salaam Port using traffic volume, VKT, VHT, V/C ratio, and LOS indicators.
- b. To evaluate the impact of Dar es Salaam Port expansion on future hinterland road network performance under existing and 20-year forecast traffic scenarios using PTV Visum.
- c. To assess the effectiveness of proposed infrastructure improvements in mitigating congestion and enhancing network performance

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Ports play a critical role in facilitating international trade and regional economic development by connecting maritime and inland transport systems. Modern ports function not only as cargo handling facilities but also as logistics hubs that support freight distribution through road, rail, and inland transport networks (Notteboom et al., 2021). The efficiency and competitiveness of a port therefore depend not only on its operational performance but also on the quality of its hinterland transport connections (Rodrigue, 2020).

Port expansion and increasing cargo throughput are often associated with growth in freight transport demand. Studies have shown that increases in port activity generate additional truck movements on access roads and freight corridors, which may contribute to congestion, increased travel times, and deterioration of roadway performance (Holguín-Veras et al., 2002) and (Duffield et al., 2020). Efficient hinterland connectivity is therefore essential for maintaining reliable freight movement and minimizing logistics costs (Wan & Luan, 2022).

Traffic performance is commonly evaluated using indicators such as traffic volume, travel speed, delay, Vehicle Kilometres Travelled (VKT), Vehicle Hours Travelled (VHT), Volume-to-Capacity (V/C) ratio, and Level of Service (LOS) ((TRB), 2010). These indicators provide a basis for assessing congestion levels and roadway operational conditions under existing and future traffic demand scenarios.

Transport modelling has become an important tool for evaluating the impacts of infrastructure development on traffic systems. Origin-Destination (OD) matrices are commonly estimated using the Gravity Model, which assumes that trip interaction increases with zone attractiveness and decreases with travel impedance (Willumsen, L. G., 2011). Traffic demand is subsequently assigned to the network using traffic assignment techniques, with User Equilibrium assignment being widely applied because it accounts for congestion effects and route choice behaviour (Wardrop, 1952).

PTV Visum is a widely used macroscopic transport planning software that supports O-D matrix development, traffic assignment, forecasting, and roadway performance evaluation (PTV Group 2023). Several studies have successfully applied PTV Visum to analyse freight transport systems, corridor performance, and future traffic scenarios (Suartawan et al., 2024) and (Yusup et al., 2025).

Previous studies have investigated port congestion, freight transport, and logistics performance (Niu et al., 2024) and (Benedecti et al., 2026). However, limited research has evaluated the long-term impacts of port expansion on hinterland road network performance using strategic traffic modelling approaches. This study addresses this gap by assessing the future effects of Dar es Salaam Port expansion on major hinterland corridors using PTV Visum and traffic performance indicators such as V/C ratio, LOS, travel speed, delay, VKT, and VHT.

3. FUTURE TRAFFIC FORECASTING

Traffic forecasting estimates future traffic demand based on existing traffic volumes and expected growth. Future traffic volume was estimated using the growth factor method.

$$T_n = T_0(1 + r)^n \tag{1}$$

where T_n is the forecast traffic volume in year n , T_0 is the base-year traffic volume, r is the annual growth rate, and n is the number of years (May et al., 2001); (Willumsen, L. G., 2011) and ((TRB), 2010).

This approach is widely applied in strategic transport planning where detailed future O-D data are unavailable.

Gravity Model for Trip Distribution

The gravity model is one of the most widely used methods for estimating O-D matrices (Cascetta, 1984). The gravity model assumes that:

Trip interaction increases with zone attractiveness;

Trip interaction decreases with travel cost or distance.

The gravity model was adopted in this study to estimate Origin-Destination (O-D) traffic demand between traffic analysis zones using observed traffic counts and travel distances between zones. (Erlander & Stewart, 1990) and (Savrasovs & Pticina, 2017). The model assumes that trip interaction increases with trip attraction and decreases with increasing travel impedance such as distance or travel time (Willumsen, L. G., 2011).

The Gravity Model is based on the analogy of Newton's law of gravitation, where interaction between two zones increases with the size or attractiveness of the zones and decreases with increasing travel impedance such as distance, travel time, or transportation cost. The model assumes that zones with high trip production and attraction generate stronger traffic interaction compared to zones separated by longer travel distances.

According (Willumsen, L. G., 2011), this function often receives the name of 'deterrence function' because it represents the disincentive to travel as distance (time) or cost increases. Popular versions for this function are: exponential function, power function and combined function as indicated below respectively.

$$f(c_{ij}) = \exp(-\beta c_{ij}) \quad (2)$$

$$f(c_{ij}) = c_{ij}^{-n} \quad (3)$$

$$f(c_{ij}) = c_{ij}^{-n} \exp(-\beta c_{ij}) \quad (4)$$

The inverse power function was adopted in this study because freight transport interactions associated with port-generated traffic tend to exhibit long-distance movement characteristics. According to (Willumsen, L. G., 2011), the power function better captures the gradual decay of freight trip interaction with distance compared to the exponential function. Figure 2 indicate the different deterrence functions

Figure 2: Different deterrence functions (Source (Willumsen, L. G., 2011))

The distance decay parameter (n) in the inverse power function was not restricted to integer values. Previous transport modelling studies have estimated values ranging between 0.6 and 3.5 depending on the characteristics of the transport system and trip purpose.(Willumsen, L. G., 2011)

To model the spatial distribution of port-generated traffic, an inverse-power gravity function with a distance decay parameter of $n = 2$ was adopted. The selected value represents moderate spatial resistance for regional road freight transport and is considered appropriate for hinterland trucking networks (Rodrigue, 2020).Therefore, the formula used to calculate each Origin-Destination (O-D) matrix cell was expressed using the inverse-power gravity model as follows:(Willumsen, L. G., 2011).

$$T_{ij} = \frac{P_i A_j}{c_{ij}^2} \tag{5}$$

Whereby;

T_{ij} = estimated trips from origin zone i to destination zone j

P_i = trip production at origin zone i

A_j = trip attraction at destination zone j

c_{ij} = travel distance/cost between zones i and j

0.6= adopted inverse-power distance decay parameter ($n = 0.6$) representing moderate freight transport spatial resistance.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a quantitative transport modelling approach to evaluate the impact of Dar es Salaam Port expansion on the performance of the hinterland road network. The study focused on four major port access corridors: Kilwa Road (T007), Nyerere Road (T024), Mandela Road (T025), and Morogoro Road (T001). Figure 3 illustrate the study area

Figure 3. Study Area (Source: Google Map)

Data collection

Primary data were collected through classified traffic counts, travel time surveys, delay surveys, and road inventory surveys, while secondary data, including cargo throughput statistics and road network information, were obtained from the Tanzania Ports Authority (TPA) and Tanzania National Roads Agency (TANROADS). The study area was divided into 20 Traffic Analysis Zones (TAZs) representing port, industrial, commercial, residential, and external gateway activities. Table 1. Illustrate the TAZs

Table 1: indicate the zone land user categories

Zone Numbers	Zone name	Land use categories	Zone classification
1	Port container area	Port	Internal zones
2	Passenger area		
3	Kurasin ICD		

4	Vingunguti	Industrial area	
5	Wherehouse-supper doll		
6	Bakhares and ICD		
7	Temeke	City Centre and Core Business Area	
8	Karia Koo		
9	Kisutu		
10	Magomeni		
11	Manzese	Residential Area	
12	Ubungo		
13	Kimara		
14	Mikocheni		
15	Tandale		
16	Mwananyamala		
17	Sinza		
18	Mbagala		
19	Kibaha	Ingoing/Outgoing to the port area	External
20	Bagamoyo		

Trip Production and Attraction Estimation

Due to the limited availability of detailed zonal origin-destination data, trip production (O_i) and attraction (D_j) values were estimated by applying land-use-based directional factors to the observed traffic count data (G_i).

According to The Geography of Transport Systems (Rodrigue, 2020), port zones (zones 1-3) were assumed to function predominantly as freight trip producers and were therefore assigned an 65% production and 35% attraction split. Industrial and warehouse zones (zones 4-6) were treated as major freight attractors and assigned a 35% production and 65% attraction split to reflect cargo storage and distribution activities.

Based on the transport modelling principles described by Modelling Transport (Willumsen, L. G., 2011), commercial zones (zones 7-10) were assigned a 35% production and 65% attraction split to represent goods delivery concentration within urban centers, while residential zones (zones 11-18) were assigned a 60% production and 40% attraction split to reflect dominant outbound commuting patterns during peak periods.

External gateway zones (zones 19-20) were assigned a balanced 50% production and 50% attraction split to represent bidirectional regional traffic exchange and maintain network equilibrium, consistent with boundary zone modelling practices recommended by the (Federal Highway Administration, 2010).The Table 2 summarize the original-destination percentage ways.

Table 2: Production-Attraction Distribution Factors for Traffic Analysis Zones

Zone Category	Functional Role	Production (O_i)	Attraction (D_j)	Basis
Port zones (1-3)	Freight production-heavy	65%	35%	Port cargo distribution and hinterland freight dispatch characteristics (Rodrigue, 2020), and DSM port freight movement data from Weighbridge
Industrial & Warehouse zones (4-6)	Freight attraction-heavy	35%	65%	Cargo storage, ICD, and logistics attraction functions (Rodrigue, 2020)
Commercial zones (7-10)	Moderate attraction-heavy	35%	65%	Urban goods delivery concentration and commercial interaction (Ortúzar & Willumsen, 2011)
Residential zones (11-18)	Production-heavy	60%	40%	Dominant outbound commuter movement during peak periods (Ortúzar & Willumsen, 2011)
External Gateway zones (19-20)	Balanced interaction	50%	50%	Boundary zone equilibrium and regional traffic exchange assumptions (FHWA, 2010)

The matrix estimation framework improved model calibration, network realism, and forecasting accuracy. Calibration was enhanced by reducing differences between assigned

traffic volumes and observed field traffic counts. Network realism was improved by representing actual congestion conditions and freight movement characteristics within the port hinterland road network. These improvements provided a more reliable and stable basis for forecasting future traffic distribution and road capacity performance.(Cascetta, 2009).

Traffic Assignment Modelling

In this study, the User Equilibrium Assignment method was adopted. Based on Wardrop's equilibrium principle, the method assumes that no driver can reduce travel time by changing routes once equilibrium is reached (Wardrop, 1952). This approach is considered more realistic for urban traffic networks because it incorporates congestion effects and route choice behaviour.

Volume Delay Function (VDF)

Traffic assignment models use volume-delay functions to represent congestion effects. The Bureau of Public Roads (BPR) function was adopted to model the relationship between traffic volume and travel time within the road network. The BPR function is expressed as follows.(Willumsen, L. G., 2011).

$$t = t_0 \left[1 + \alpha \left(\frac{v}{c} \right)^\beta \right] \tag{6}$$

t = congested travel time

t_0 = free-flow travel time

v = traffic volume

c = roadway capacity

α and β = calibration parameter

In this study, the Bureau of Public Roads (BPR) volume-delay function was used during traffic assignment to represent the effect of congestion on travel time within the hinterland road network. The function was integrated within the User Equilibrium Assignment procedure in PTV Visum to simulate traffic flow redistribution under increasing port-generated traffic demand. The BPR function enabled the estimation of congestion effects, travel delays, and roadway performance under existing and future traffic conditions.

Application of PTV Visum in Port Traffic Studies

Several studies have applied PTV Visum in freight transport and port traffic analysis. (Yusup et al., 2025) and (Benedecti et al., 2026) used PTV Visum for macroscopic traffic simulation associated with infrastructure development, while (Suartawan et al., 2024) demonstrated its capability in strategic traffic assignment and future traffic forecasting. PTV Visum is particularly suitable for strategic traffic forecasting, freight traffic modelling, corridor performance analysis, and future scenario evaluation.

In this study, PTV Visum was used to develop the hinterland road network model, assign current and future traffic demand, evaluate traffic performance indicators, and assess the impact of future port expansion on roadway capacity and traffic operations.

Model Calibration and Validation

Model calibration and validation were conducted to ensure that the developed traffic model reasonably represented observed field traffic conditions before future forecasting analysis was performed. The validation process involved comparing modelled traffic volumes obtained from the PTV Visum assignment model with observed traffic count data collected from the study corridors.

The Geoffrey E. Havers (GEH) statistic was used to measure the agreement between modelled and observed traffic volumes and was expressed as:

$$GEH = \sqrt{\frac{2(M-C)^2}{M+C}} \quad (7)$$

Where:

M = modelled traffic volume;

C = observed traffic count.

The coefficient of determination (R^2) was used to evaluate the strength of correlation between observed and modelled traffic volumes and was expressed as:

$$R^2 = \left[\frac{\sum(O_i - \bar{O})(M_i - \bar{M})}{\sqrt{\sum(O_i - \bar{O})^2 \sum(M_i - \bar{M})^2}} \right]^2 \quad (8)$$

Where:

O_i = observed traffic volume;

M_i = modelled traffic volume;

\bar{O} = mean observed traffic volume;

\bar{M} = mean modelled traffic volume.

The developed model was considered acceptable when at least 85% of the traffic count locations achieved $GEH < 5$, and the coefficient of determination satisfied $R^2 > 0.75$. These validation criteria ensured that the calibrated model provided a reliable basis for future traffic forecasting and traffic performance evaluation under port expansion scenarios.

Scenario Development

Four scenarios were analysed: (i) existing conditions without port expansion, (ii) existing conditions with port expansion, (iii) a 20-year forecast with port expansion, and (iv) a 20-year forecast incorporating proposed infrastructure improvements. The scenarios were simulated in PTV Visum by adjusting traffic demand and network characteristics to reflect future freight growth and improvement measures. Network performance was evaluated using Volume-to-Capacity (V/C) ratio, Level of Service (LOS), travel speed, and traffic delay. The scenario analysis was used to identify critical congestion corridors and assess the effectiveness of infrastructure interventions in improving long-term network performance.

5. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the results and discussion obtained from the traffic modelling and simulation conducted using PTV Visum. The analysis evaluates the performance of the major hinterland road corridors serving Dar es Salaam Port, namely Kilwa road (T007), Nyerere road (T024), Mandela road (T025), and Morogoro road (T001), under existing and future traffic demand conditions.

Model Calibration and Validation

The calibration and validation results demonstrate a significant improvement in model performance. Prior to calibration, the model produced a GEH value of 34.03 and an R² value of 0.28, indicating poor agreement between observed and modelled traffic volumes. Following the calibration process, the GEH value was reduced to 1.58, while the coefficient of determination increased to 0.99, demonstrating excellent agreement between observed and modelled traffic data.

The calibrated results satisfy the validation criteria recommended in the PTV Visum Guidelines, which suggest that GEH values below 5.0 indicate acceptable model performance. Similar findings have been reported by (Garber & Hoel, 2015) (Suartawan et al., 2024), and (Willumsen, L. G., 2011) who emphasized that traffic models should accurately reproduce existing traffic conditions before being applied for forecasting purposes. Therefore, the calibrated model is considered sufficiently reliable for evaluating the impacts of Dar es Salaam Port expansion and future traffic growth on the hinterland road network. Table 3 and 4 for GEH and R² respectively.

Table 3 GEH validation results

Road link	Zone name	Count station	Model Traffic	Observed Traffic
Kilwa (T007)	Kurasini	Sabasaba	1114	1038
Nyerere (T024)	Wherehouse	Superdoll	1240	1098
Mandela (T025)	Bakharesa	Bakharesa	1436	1697
Morogoro (T001)	Kibaha	Fire station	1338	1182
Total			5128	5015
GEH			1.58	

Table 4: R² validation results

Road link	Zone name	Count station	Model Traffic	Observed Traffic
Kilwa (T007)	Kurasini	Sabasaba	1114	1038

Nyerere (T024)	Wherehouse	Superdoll	1240	1098
Mandela (T025)	Bakharesa	Bakharesa	1436	1697
Morogoro (T001)	Kibaha	Fire station	1338	1182
Total			5128	5015
R²			0.99	

Scenario 1: Existing traffic conditions without port expansion

Scenario 1 represents the baseline traffic condition of the study network before the effects of future port expansion and projected traffic growth are introduced. Under this scenario, traffic demand consists primarily of existing commuter traffic, commercial activities, and normal freight movement associated with current port operations. The scenario provides a reference condition against which future traffic growth and improvement scenarios can be compared. Table 5 presents the results of the key traffic performance indicators for the baseline scenario, including traffic volume, Vehicle Kilometers Travelled (VKT), Vehicle Hours Travelled (VHT), Volume-to-Capacity (V/C) ratio, and Level of Service (LOS) while Table 6 illustrate travel speed, delay.

Table 5: Performance indicators without port expansion

Road link	Performance indicators				
	Veh/hr	VHT	VKT	V/C	LOS
Kilwa (T007)	1114	37	1367	0.62	B
Nyerere (T024)	1240	104	3535	0.69	B
Mandela (T025)	1436	29	907	0.80	C
Morogoro (T001)	1338	113	3680	0.74	C

Table 6: Travel speed and delay time without port expansion

Road link	Performance indicator of travel speed and delay time				
	km	Av speed km/hr	Actual time min	Free time min	Delay time min
Kilwa (T007)	1.227	36.95	1.99	1.47	0.52
Nyerere (T024)	2.852	33.99	5.03	3.42	1.61
Mandela (T025)	0.631	31.28	1.21	0.76	0.45

Morogoro (T001)	2.766	32.57	5.10	3.32	1.78
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Tables 5 and 6 indicate that the major hinterland corridors currently operate under acceptable traffic conditions, with V/C ratios ranging from 0.62 to 0.80 and LOS B-C. Mandela Road (T025) recorded the highest traffic volume (1,436 veh/hr) and V/C ratio (0.80), indicating the highest level of corridor utilization, while Kilwa Road (T007) showed the best operating conditions with a V/C ratio of 0.62 and LOS B.

Morogoro Road (T001) and Nyerere Road (T024) recorded the highest VHT values of 113 and 104 hours, respectively, as well as the highest VKT values, reflecting their importance as major traffic distribution corridors. Average travel speeds ranged from 31.28 to 36.95 km/h, while delays remained relatively low, varying between 0.45 and 1.78 minutes. The highest delay was observed on Morogoro Road, followed by Nyerere Road.

Overall, the results suggest that the existing hinterland road network can accommodate current traffic demand. However, Mandela Road, Morogoro Road, and Nyerere Road are already operating at relatively high utilization levels and may become critical congestion points as freight traffic increases following the expansion of Dar es Salaam Port.

Scenario 2: Existing traffic conditions with port expansion

Scenario 2 represents the initial impact of Dar es Salaam Port expansion following the implementation of the Dar es Salaam Maritime Gateway Project (DMGP). Under this scenario, increased cargo throughput generates additional heavy truck trips, resulting in higher freight traffic demand across the hinterland road network. The introduction of this freight demand through the User Equilibrium traffic assignment model increases traffic volumes and operational pressure on the major port access corridors.

Based on historical traffic count data from Veterinary filling station count station of year 2018 and 2021, an annual growth rate of 3% was adopted for general traffic demand. In contrast, analysis of port cargo throughput data indicated an average annual growth rate of 13%, reflecting the expected increase in freight movement associated with port expansion. The projected freight growth was incorporated into the traffic demand model to assess its impact on road network performance. Table 7 and 8 illustrate the results

Table 7: Performance indicators with port expansion

Road link	Performance indicators				
	Veh/hr	VHT	VKT	V/C	LOS
Kilwa (T007)	1176	41	1442	0.65	B
Nyerere (T024)	1389	126	3962	0.77	C
Mandela (T025)	1619	36	1022	0.90	D

Morogoro (T001)	1515	143	4190	0.84	D
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Table 8: Travel speed and delay time with port expansion

Road link	Performance indicator of travel speed and delay time				
	km	Av speed km/hr	Actual time min	Free time min	Delay time min
Kilwa (T007)	1.227	35.17	2.09	1.47	0.62
Nyerere (T024)	2.852	31.44	5.44	3.42	2.02
Mandela (T025)	0.631	28.39	1.33	0.76	0.58
Morogoro (T001)	2.766	29.30	5.66	3.32	2.34

Tables 7 and 8 show that port expansion increased traffic demand and reduced corridor performance. Mandela Road recorded the highest traffic volume (1,619 veh/hr) and V/C ratio (0.90), while Morogoro Road recorded the highest VHT (143 hours) and delay (2.34 minutes). Average travel speeds decreased to between 28.39 km/h and 35.17 km/h, and LOS deteriorated from B–C under existing conditions to B-D following port expansion. These results indicate that additional port-generated freight traffic increased congestion and reduced operational efficiency, particularly on Mandela and Morogoro Roads.

Scenario 3: 20 -Year future forecast with port expansion

Scenario 3 evaluates the future performance of the hinterland road network over a 20-year planning horizon under continued port expansion without the implementation of additional road infrastructure improvements. The scenario combines the projected growth in Dar es Salaam Port cargo throughput with the anticipated increase in general traffic demand, while maintaining the existing road network configuration and capacity. Table 9 and 10 illustrate results.

Table 9: Performance indicators of 20- years forecasting with expansion

Road link	Performance indicators				
	Veh/hr	VHT	VKT	V/C	LOS
Kilwa (T007)	1907	99	2339	1.06	F
Nyerere (T024)	2407	382	6863	1.34	F

Mandela (T025)	2837	124	1791	1.58	F
Morogoro (T001)	3017	635	8346	1.68	F

Table 10: Travel speed and delay time of 20- years forecasting with expansion

Road link	Performance indicator travel speed and delay time				
	km	Av speed km/hr	Actual time min	Free time min	Delay time min
Kilwa (T007)	1.227	23.63	3.12	1.47	1.64
Nyerere (T024)	2.852	17.97	9.52	3.42	6.10
Mandela (T025)	0.631	14.44	2.62	0.76	1.86
Morogoro (T001)	2.766	13.14	12.63	3.32	9.31

Tables 9 and IV.10 show a substantial deterioration in network performance under the 20-year forecast scenario with port expansion. Traffic volumes increased significantly across all corridors, resulting in V/C ratios ranging from 1.06 to 1.68 and LOS F on all major routes. Morogoro Road recorded the highest traffic volume (3,017 veh/hr), V/C ratio (1.68), and VHT (635 hours), indicating severe congestion and oversaturated operating conditions. Similarly, Mandela Road and Nyerere Road experienced high V/C ratios of 1.58 and 1.34, respectively.

The increase in traffic demand led to significant reductions in travel speed and increases in delay. Average speeds declined to between 13.14 km/h and 23.63 km/h, while delays increased to between 1.64 and 9.31 minutes. Morogoro Road experienced the highest delay (9.31 minutes), followed by Nyerere Road (6.10 minutes). Overall, the results indicate that the existing road infrastructure will be unable to accommodate future traffic demand generated by port expansion, resulting in severe congestion, reduced mobility, and poor network performance.

Scenario 4: 20-Year forecast with targeted infrastructure interventions

Scenario 4 evaluates the future performance of the hinterland road network under the projected 2045 traffic demand with the implementation of proposed infrastructure improvement measures. The scenario was developed to address the congestion and capacity deficiencies identified under Scenario 3. Table 11 and 12 illustrate the results

Table 11: Performance indicators of 20- years forecasting with Targeted Infrastructure Interventions

Road link	Performance indicators				
	Veh/hr	VHT	VKT	V/C	LOS
Kilwa (T007)	1907	59	2339	0.53	A
Nyerere (T024)	2407	198	6863	0.67	B
Mandela (T025)	2837	54	1791	0.79	C
Morogoro (T001)	3017	284	8346	0.84	D

Table 12: Travel speed and delay time of 20- years forecasting with Targeted Infrastructure Interventions

Road link	Performance indicator travel speed and delay time				
	km	Av speed km/hr	Actual time min	Free time min	Delay time min
Kilwa (T007)	1.227	39.64	1.86	1.47	0.38
Nyerere (T024)	2.852	34.66	4.94	3.42	1.51
Mandela (T025)	0.631	33.17	1.14	0.76	0.38
Morogoro (T001)	2.766	29.39	5.65	3.32	2.33

Tables 11 and 12 show that the proposed infrastructure improvements significantly enhanced network performance under the 20-year forecast traffic demand. Although traffic volumes remained unchanged, V/C ratios decreased from the congested levels observed under the do-nothing scenario to between 0.53 and 0.84, resulting in improved LOS ranging from A to D. Kilwa Road achieved the best operating condition with a V/C ratio of 0.53 and LOS A, while Morogoro Road recorded the highest V/C ratio (0.84) and operated at LOS D.

The improvement measures also reduced travel times and delays while increasing average travel speeds. Average speeds increased to between 29.39 km/h and 39.64 km/h, compared with 13.14-23.63 km/h under the do-nothing scenario. Similarly, delays

decreased substantially to between 0.38 and 2.33 minutes. The results indicate that the proposed interventions effectively mitigated future congestion, improved traffic operations, and restored acceptable performance levels across the major hinterland corridors despite continued growth in port-generated traffic.

Implications of Dar es Salaam port expansion on hinterland corridor performance

The results indicate that Dar es Salaam Port expansion will significantly influence the performance of the hinterland corridor. The corridor-level results presented in Figure 4 reveal that Morogoro Road experienced the highest traffic demand, increasing from 1,338 veh/hr to 3,017 veh/hr, followed by Mandela Road, which increased from 1,436 veh/hr to 2,837 veh/hr. This indicates that these corridors will carry a substantial proportion of future port-generated traffic.

Figure 4: Indicate the volume variation under corridor level

The increase in traffic demand resulted in a significant deterioration in network performance. As shown in Figure 5 Corridor-level analysis shows that Morogoro Road recorded the highest V/C ratio of 1.68, followed by Mandela Road (1.58), Nyerere Road (1.34), and Kilwa Road (1.06). These values indicate that all corridors exceeded their practical capacity limits and operated under congested conditions. The increase in V/C ratio was accompanied by a corresponding decline in Level of Service (LOS). Under existing conditions, the corridors operated at LOS B-C, reflecting stable traffic flow and acceptable operating conditions. However, under the 20-year do-nothing scenario, all corridors deteriorated to LOS F, indicating oversaturated traffic conditions characterized by severe congestion, unstable traffic flow, excessive delays, and substantial reductions in travel speed. This demonstrates that the projected growth in port-generated traffic will significantly degrade corridor performance unless additional capacity improvements are implemented.

Figure 5: Indicate the volume-to capacity ratio variation under corridor level

The impact of congestion is further reflected in travel speed performance. Figure 6. at corridor level, Morogoro Road recorded the lowest average speed (13 km/h), followed by Mandela Road (14 km/h), Nyerere Road (18 km/h), and Kilwa Road (24 km/h). These results indicate severe traffic congestion and reduced mobility across the network.

Figure 6: Indicate the average speed variation under corridor level

Similarly, average network delay increased at corridor-level results Figure 7 show that Morogoro Road experienced the highest delay of 9.31 minutes, while Nyerere Road recorded 6.10 minutes. In contrast, Kilwa Road and Mandela Road experienced lower delays of approximately 1.68 and 1.64 minutes, respectively. The increase in delay corresponds closely with the reduction in travel speeds and increase in V/C ratios.

Figure 7: Indicate the average speed variation under corridor level

The deterioration in operating conditions is also evident from the Vehicle Hours Travelled (VHT) results. Figure 8 at Corridor-level analysis indicates that Morogoro Road recorded the highest VHT value of 483.75 hours, followed by Nyerere Road (approximately 420 hours), reflecting longer travel times caused by congestion.

Figure 8: Indicate the hour variation under corridor level

Likewise, average corridor-level VKT increased most significantly on Morogoro Road (from 3,680 km to 8,346 km) and Nyerere Road (from 3,535 km to 6,863 km), demonstrating their importance as primary freight distribution corridors. Figure 9 shows corridor level.

Figure 9: Indicate the hour variation under corridor level

The mitigation scenario demonstrates that future congestion can be substantially reduced through infrastructure improvements. All Figures 4-9, above shows that average network V/C ratio decreased from 1.41 to 0.71, average speed increased from 17.29 km/h to 34.21 km/h, average delay decreased from 9.31 minutes to 1.15 minutes, and VHT reduced from 310 hours to 148.75 hours. Corridor-level results indicate that speeds increased to 40 km/h on Kilwa Road, 35 km/h on Nyerere Road, 33 km/h on Mandela Road, and 29 km/h on Morogoro Road, while V/C ratios declined to acceptable levels ranging between 0.53 and 0.84. Consequently, corridor operating conditions improved from LOS F to LOS A-D.

These findings demonstrate that although Dar es Salaam Port expansion will generate substantial freight traffic growth, the resulting impacts on corridor performance can be effectively managed through timely investments in corridor capacity enhancement and freight mobility improvements.

6. CONCLUSION

This study evaluated the impact of Dar es Salaam Port expansion on the performance of major hinterland road corridors, namely Kilwa Road (T007), Nyerere Road (T024), Mandela Road (T025), and Morogoro Road (T001), using a macroscopic traffic modelling approach in PTV Visum. The developed model was successfully calibrated and validated, achieving a GEH value of 1.58 and an R² value of 0.99, indicating excellent agreement between observed and modelled traffic volumes.

The results showed that the existing road network generally operates under acceptable conditions, with V/C ratios ranging from 0.62 to 0.80 and LOS B-C. However, the introduction of additional freight traffic associated with port expansion increased traffic volumes, travel delays, VHT, and V/C ratios while reducing travel speeds and corridor operating conditions.

Under the 20-year forecast scenario without infrastructure improvements, all major corridors deteriorated to LOS F, with V/C ratios ranging from 1.06 to 1.68. Morogoro Road and Mandela Road were identified as the most critical corridors, experiencing the highest congestion levels, travel delays, and traffic volumes. Average network speed declined from 33.69 km/h to 17.29 km/h, while average network VHT increased from 70.75 hours to 310 hours, indicating severe deterioration in network performance.

The implementation of targeted infrastructure interventions substantially improved corridor performance. Average network speed increased to 34.21 km/h, average V/C ratio decreased to 0.71, and corridor operating conditions improved from LOS F to LOS A-D. The findings demonstrate that although Dar es Salaam Port expansion will generate significant freight traffic growth, its adverse impacts on the hinterland road network can be effectively mitigated through timely capacity enhancement and traffic management measures.

6.1 Recommendations

1. Road Capacity Enhancement

Capacity improvement measures, including corridor widening and additional traffic lanes, should be implemented on Kilwa Road, Nyerere Road, Mandela Road, and Morogoro Road to accommodate future freight traffic demand generated by port expansion.

2. Dedicated Freight Facilities

Dedicated freight lanes and improved truck access facilities should be introduced along major port access corridors to reduce conflicts between freight and passenger traffic and improve overall traffic operations.

3. Integrated Port-Transport Planning

Future port development projects should be coordinated with hinterland transport infrastructure planning to ensure that increases in cargo handling capacity are matched by adequate road network capacity.

4. Future Research

Further studies should incorporate economic impact assessment, environmental effects, freight mode shift analysis, and multimodal transport integration to provide a more comprehensive evaluation of the long-term implications of Dar es Salaam Port expansion on regional transportation systems.

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